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Review Article

Art of Parenting vs Parental Child Abuse – Choose a Right Path

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Abstract: Incidence of child abuse is increasing day by day. Parents, close relatives, friends or neighbors are frequently involved in it. Under reporting of incidence, social stigma, fear, etc. are widely prevalent in the society for child abuse. In this review article, we tried to discuss various parental child abuse and key features of art of parenting to overcome such issues. Information regarding what parents can do to avoid child abuse can be disseminated via public lectures, role play, educational videos etc. among parents and children to identify, prevent and avoid child abuse.

Key words: Art of parenting, Parental child abuse, Right path.

Introduction: Many times we come across newspaper headlines mentioning parental child abuse or ignorance of child by parents or various surveys on parenting. There are various ways by which parents are knowingly or unknowingly abusing the child. Seven types of parental child abuse are discussed here briefly to get overview regarding various forms of child abuse [1].

Physical abuse: Intimidating by standing over, isolation of child by not supporting in difficult times, restraint in a close room, aggressive hitting, endanger

verbal threats to child etc. are various forms of physical abuse to child [1].

Mental abuse: Rage on child without reason, lying to child which creates doubt in memory of child, Silent treatment punishment by ignoring illness of child or not providing timely treatment, projecting problems like dumping own issues on child, twisting the truth to blame child, playing victim card when rest all fails, etc. are various ways of mental abuse to child.

Verbal abuse: Use of high tone of voice against children, interrogating child on various issues, creating blame game, constant criticism, not asking apology when needed are verbal abuse of child by parents [1].

Emotional abuse: Creating embarrassment or shame to child by sharing private moments of child to others without willingness of child, producing sense of insecurity in child, self-feeling of excessive guilt, increasing anxiety by frequent questioning, restricting purposefully what child likes, etc. are types of emotional abuse [1].

Financial abuse: Forbidden the access to gifts and money what child got from others, Opening bank account in child's name

without knowledge of child, not providing adequate money for career building of child, allocation of strict budget for day to day activity, credit card or bill in the name of child, etc. are financial abuse [1].

Sexual abuse: Unwanted or embarrassing sexual act in front of child as part of grooming, molestation by touching private parts, rape, sadistic behavior, compel child to watch pornography, etc. various forms of sexual abuse are present in the society [1].

Spiritual abuse: Blind obedience of order given, diving friends on basis of religion, public performance without willingness of child, strict adherence to parents' command, strict following of religious rituals, etc. may be considered as spiritual abuse [1].

Effective parenting: Parents must teach their child what is good and what is bad as good in - good out on the contrary garbage in - garbage out. Parents have to identify bad association vs good association of child because good association make child flourish while bad association will destroy the future. Inculcating good habits among child is prime importance of parents like reading books, helping others

while excessive watching TV or mobile must be avoided. Teach child how to control or win lust of anything because if lust will satisfy it may turn into greed lie substance abuse [2, 3] and if lust will not satisfy it create anger. Good thought leads to good action, good action converts into good habit, good habit turns into good character and good character will land up in good destiny. Parents must teach their children how to manage mind to avoid depression, anxiety, fear, greed, loneliness among children. Give unconditional love to child till the age of five years, Teach them discipline and etiquette between age of six to fifteen years, from sixteen years onwards be friend of your child. Those parents who do not educate their children are their enemies. So try to provide best opportunity to your children to mould their future [4].

What parents can do: Give your time to child, teach discipline to child, educate them, examine carefully behavior of child, Teach children their right, support child abuse prevention program, learn to know the sign of child abuse, know what child abuse is, report the abuse to authority and be supportive to child by investing time, money and love [5].

Conclusion: Good parenting is an art to learn and it is very much needed in this current era to support and nurture the child. Instead of abusing the child, showing them right direction and guiding on the path of life is prime role of parents. If parents will choose the right path then child will be benefitted by their parenting but if parents will abuse then child will be destroyed. Educational programs like public lectures, debate as well various case scenarios of subjects, role play should be required to increase knowledge and awareness among parents and children [6]. Various issues have emerged during COVID times regarding compulsory vaccination to child [7], eye problems due to e learning [8], excessive use of social media during lockdown [9, 10, 11], etc. which need to be dealt as parents carefully. Various funding agencies should come up to support research in the field off parental child abuse [12].

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